

اسلام کا نظام الاوقاف ائمہ اربعہ کی نظر میں

**THE SYSTEM OF ENDOWMENTS OF ISLAM
IN THE EYES OF THE FOUR IMAMS****Abdul Haq Haqani (ORCID ID: 0009-0001-8791-4985)**

Ph.D. Research Scholar, Faculty of Islamic Studies, University of Baluchistan, Quetta.

Raheel Ahmed (ORCID ID: 0009-0009-7201-8852)

Assistant Director, National Book Foundation.

ABSTRACT

In summary, the brief definition of waqf is to give alms in the name of Allah to some of one's property etc. so that the thing exists and certain people or common people continue to benefit from it so that as long as the thing exists then the person who knows (the giver of charity) is rewarded. On the one hand, helping people, on the other hand, it is a reward. In the discussion of waqf, each of the four Imams has mentioned his own specific definition. In principle and method of inference, there is a change in each style, the effect of which must be based on the sub-rules. According to As far as the legal status of waqf is concerned, the problem is that there are many legal arguments on the legitimacy of waqf. The jurists have written specific conditions regarding waqf, some of which are related to nafs waqf, some are related to waqf, some are related to waqf, and some are related to waqf, and there are some other conditions which are related to those who are waqf. After that we have mentioned here some specific issues which were related to the school of thought of each of the four Imams. Looking at the books of Shariat Islam, it is clear that the work done by Nizam-ul-Awqaf of Islam has not been done before and no one will be able to do it later-In this article, we have researched the methodology and methodology of research, narrative and research, with the texts of Qur'an and Hadith, the books of the four Imams have been researched with a view to the source. With the introduction of the "Government Waqf Property Bill" the importance and necessity of the subject began to increase, which can be gauged from the fact that every small and big Darul Iftaa of Pakistan had some need on this subject.

Keywords: Waqf, Jurists, Shariat, Aima e Arba, Charity.

کلیدی الفاظ: وقف، فقہاء، شریعت، ائمہ اربعہ، صدقہ۔

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7767727